

Experimental Study on the Regulation of Microstructure and Properties of SLM Formed TC4 Titanium Alloy by Heat Treatment

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Abstract:

This study addresses the strength-ductility tradeoff in selective laser melting fabricated TC4 titanium alloy caused by the formation of nonequilibrium martensitic alpha prime phase during rapid solidification. A solution treatment and aging process was applied to modify the microstructure. Specimens underwent solution treatment between 950 and 990 degrees Celsius followed by water quenching, and aging at 500 or 550 degrees Celsius. Microstructure was analyzed using MIPAR deep learning for alpha phase quantification. Mechanical and corrosion properties were assessed through tensile tests, Vickers hardness measurements, and electrochemical testing in 3.5 percent sodium chloride solution. Results demonstrate that the 990 degrees Celsius solution treatment followed by 500 degrees Celsius aging produced a high fraction of 86.2 percent equiaxed primary alpha phase. This refined structure led to a remarkable 126 percent

improvement in elongation, increasing from 4.9 percent in the asfabricated state to 11.1 percent, while maintaining high tensile strength of 870 megapascals and hardness of 312 HV. Corrosion resistance was also significantly enhanced, evidenced by a 68 percent reduction in corrosion current density, along with increases of 0.25 volts in pitting potential and 0.32 volts in breakdown potential of the passive film. This work demonstrates that solution treatment and aging heat treatment effectively optimizes the microstructure of selective laser melting processed TC4 alloy, achieving simultaneous improvement in both ductility and corrosion resistance without strength compromise. The strategy provides a viable processing route for manufacturing critical components in aerospace and biomedical applications that demand complex geometries, superior damage tolerance, and excellent corrosion resistance.

Keywords: Titanium alloy; Treatment; Microstructure; Corrosion protection; Quantitative analysis; Surface hardness; Deep learning

1. INTRODUCTION

Ti6Al4V (commonly designated as TC4) is extensively utilized in the aerospace sector due to its exceptional specific strength, high specific modulus, outstanding impact resistance, and excellent anti-corrosion properties. With the growing imperative for aircraft weight reduction, the efficient and cost-effective production of increasingly refined and intricate designs using this metallic material has emerged as a significant challenge. Conventional titanium alloy manufacturing processes, such as melting or rolling, struggle to meet the demands of producing such high-end components. While casting enables the production of complex-shaped parts, inherent defects like shrinkage cavities and porosity detrimentally affect part performance. Forging can improve the material's internal structure and enhance mechanical properties, but it is difficult to achieve one-step precision forming of complex geometries, often necessitating extensive subsequent machining, which leads to low material utilization and high production costs.

In contrast, Selective Laser Melting (SLM) technology demonstrates superior technical advantages owing to its unique additive manufacturing principles. This technique employs a high-energy laser beam to precisely melt and consolidate metal powder layer by layer. It not only overcomes the limitations of traditional machining regarding complex geometries, enabling the direct fabrication of arbitrary three-dimensional components, but also significantly shortens product development cycles due to its mold-free nature. Compared to conventional methods, SLM offers high material utilization efficiency, thereby minimizing waste and effectively optimizing

production costs [1-2]. Furthermore, by accurately adjusting process parameters such as laser energy density and scanning speed, SLM can precisely control the internal and surface microstructure of components. The resulting TC4 alloy parts exhibit excellent comprehensive properties, including superior compressive strength, good ductility, and corrosion resistance. Consequently, SLM technology has successfully overcome the technical bottlenecks associated with traditional manufacturing processes for TC4 titanium alloy, markedly expanding its application boundaries in aerospace precision component manufacturing. This technological advancement not only fosters innovation in lightweight, high-performance titanium alloy parts for aerospace applications but has also established SLM as a forefront of international additive manufacturing research, garnering widespread attention from both academia and industry [3].

Although TC4 alloy fabricated via SLM can achieve high yield and tensile strength, the rapid cooling inherent to the process leads to the formation of an acicular martensitic α' phase, which possesses high strength but low toughness. This microstructural feature distinctly differs from that of forged TC4 alloy and consequently impedes its broader application. This acicular α' phase has been extensively documented to pose two primary challenges related to corrosion resistance: (1) The high microstructural heterogeneity (e.g., compositional and stress differences between the α' phase and residual β phase) significantly increases the risk of forming local electrochemical micro-cells in corrosive environments, particularly in chloride-containing media, where it readily initiates localized corrosion such as pitting and crevice corrosion; (2)

The high residual stresses and dislocation density can compromise the stability of the passive film and increase susceptibility to stress corrosion cracking (SCC) [4-5].

Current research indicates that post-process heat treatment of SLM-fabricated TC4 alloy can transform the acicular α' phase into equiaxed or lamellar α phase, while also reducing residual stresses, thereby improving toughness. Theoretically, a homogeneous duplex microstructure can also diminish electrochemical heterogeneity, promote the formation of a denser and more stable passive film (enriched with protective Al_2O_3 and V oxides), and reduce the propensity for localized corrosion initiation (e.g., pitting). The surface properties of the material, particularly hardness, microstructural homogeneity, and residual stress state, are critical factors determining its corrosion resistance in service environments. For SLM-formed TC4 components deployed in corrosion-sensitive environments (e.g., aircraft structures, marine platforms) or for long-term human implantation (e.g., orthopedic/dental implants), the precise tailoring of surface microstructure via heat treatment to achieve synergistically optimized mechanical properties and corrosion resistance holds significant engineering importance.

Existing studies confirm that heat treatment can decompose the metastable α' phase in SLM-formed TC4 alloy, transforming it into equiaxed or lamellar α phase and effectively relieving residual stresses, thereby enhancing the alloy's toughness and corrosion resistance. However, conventional heat treatment processes exhibit notable limitations: Solution treatment at 700°C fails to completely eliminate the α' phase, making an ideal strength-toughness balance difficult to achieve [6]; Increasing the

solution temperature to 800°C promotes α' phase transformation, yet some untransformed residual phase persists, preventing significant enhancement of overall performance; Further elevation to 1050°C readily leads to the formation of coarse Widmanstätten structures, causing a deterioration in material ductility and similarly failing to effectively improve service performance [7]. Additionally, traditional quantitative metallographic analysis predominantly relies on manual statistical methods, which are highly subjective and can incur errors exceeding 15%, impeding the precise establishment of quantitative process-structure-property relationships and thus constraining further optimization of heat treatment parameters [8-11].

Addressing the aforementioned challenges, this research systematically investigates SLM-formed TC4 alloy, applying solution treatments across a range of 950–990°C (in 10°C increments) followed by aging at either 500°C or 550°C. The MIPAR deep learning module (U-Net model) is employed to achieve accurate quantification of the α phase morphology and volume fraction. The effects of the heat treatment parameters on microstructure, mechanical properties, and corrosion resistance are analyzed, aiming to elucidate the mechanisms through which optimized microstructures enhance corrosion resistance. This study provides theoretical and experimental support for the application of SLM-fabricated TC4 in fields such as aerospace and biomedical engineering.

2. EXPERIMENTAL MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Preparation And Characterization Of SLM-formed TC4 Titanium Alloy

The TC4 titanium alloy powder used in the experiment was prepared by gas atomization. This process produces powder with high sphericity and good fluidity, effectively avoiding issues of powder agglomeration during the SLM process and ensuring forming quality. The particle size range was strictly controlled between 15 and 53 μm , meeting the compatibility requirements for powder size in SLM. The forming equipment was a Renishaw AM250 metal 3D printing system, equipped with a stable fiber laser source that allows precise control of laser energy output, guaranteeing the dimensional accuracy of the fabricated components. The entire forming process was conducted under a high-purity argon atmosphere (99.999%) to create an inert protective environment, completely isolating the process from air. This prevents oxidation of the TC4 titanium alloy powder and the formed specimens at high temperatures, avoiding the formation of oxides that could detrimentally affect the material's subsequent mechanical properties and corrosion resistance. Specimen preparation followed the SLM process parameters optimized through extensive preliminary experiments. The specific parameters were: laser power of 280 W, scanning speed of 1200 mm/s, hatch spacing of 0.15 mm, and a layer thickness of 50 μm . This parameter set ensures sufficient powder melting while avoiding balling defects caused by over-melting. Tensile specimens with final dimensions of 30 mm \times 20 mm \times 3 mm were fabricated. The specimen dimensions were designed in accordance with GB/T 228.1-2021 "Metallic materials—Tensile testing—Part 1: Method of test at room temperature" to

ensure the standardization and comparability of subsequent tensile test data [12].

Figure 1. Tensile specimen of TC4 titanium alloy fabricated by SLM process

The chemical composition of the SLM-formed TC4 titanium alloy is shown in Table 1. In the table, Ti is the matrix element. Aluminum (Al) serves to stabilize the α phase and enhance the strength of the alloy, while Vanadium (V) stabilizes the β phase and improves the plasticity of the alloy. Iron (Fe) and Carbon (C) are impurity elements, and their contents are strictly controlled at low levels to prevent the formation of brittle phases within the alloy due to excessive impurities, which would adversely affect the overall comprehensive performance.

Table 1 Chemical composition of the SLM-formed TC4 titanium alloy

Element	Ti	Al	V	Fe	C
Mass Fraction	88.65	6.15	4.00	0.15	0.05

Following heat treatment, the specimens underwent surface preparation to achieve a surface roughness suitable for metallographic observation. Subsequently, they were etched using Kroll's reagent. Microstructural features were observed and images were captured using a PhenomXL scanning electron microscope (from the Netherlands). Room-temperature tensile tests were conducted using an Instron 5982 universal testing machine at a crosshead speed of 2 mm/min. For each processing condition, three parallel specimens were prepared and tested; the average value was calculated to

minimize random test errors and ensure the reliability of the mechanical property data. Surface hardness of the specimens was measured using an HVS-1000 Vickers hardness tester under a 500 gf load with a dwell time of 10 s. Five indents were made on different areas of each specimen's surface, avoiding edges and defects, and the average value was taken as the final hardness to ensure representative results.

Electrochemical tests were performed using a CHI660E electrochemical workstation, known for its high precision and stability, enabling accurate detection of electrochemical signals. A 3.5% NaCl solution was used as the corrosive medium. This concentration is similar to the salt content in seawater, simulating the service environments encountered in aerospace and biomedical applications, thus aligning with the material's practical application requirements. The test temperature was controlled at 25°C. Key parameters, including the self-corrosion current density, pitting potential, and passivation film breakdown voltage, were extracted from the potentiodynamic polarization curves. A lower self-corrosion current density indicates a lower corrosion rate; a higher pitting potential signifies better resistance to pitting corrosion; and a higher passivation film breakdown voltage suggests greater stability of the surface passive film. For each heat treatment process, three parallel specimens were tested, and the average value of the parameters was taken as the final result to reduce experimental randomness and ensure the repeatability and reliability of the corrosion resistance data, thereby providing a quantitative basis for subsequent analysis of the influence of microstructural characteristics on corrosion resistance.

2.2 Optimization Of Solution And Aging Heat Treatment Process

To achieve a balanced control of strength and toughness in the SLM-formed TC4 alloy, a solution and aging heat treatment process was designed, taking into account its $\alpha+\beta$ two-phase region characteristics. The influence of the process on microstructure and properties was investigated by systematically adjusting temperature parameters.

As shown in Figure 2, the solution treatment stage was conducted within the temperature range of 950–990°C, divided into five temperature gradients at 10°C intervals: 950°C, 960°C, 970°C, 980°C, and 990°C. Each temperature was held for 1 hour. The 1-hour holding time was set to ensure uniform temperature distribution within the alloy, promote complete dissolution of the β phase, and avoid incomplete microstructural transformation or compositional segregation due to insufficient holding. High-purity argon was continuously supplied during the holding period to prevent oxidation of the specimens at high temperatures. Immediately after holding, water quenching was employed instead of furnace cooling. The reason for rapid water quenching is to suppress the premature precipitation of the β phase into the α phase, allowing the alloy to obtain a supersaturated β solid solution. This lays the foundation for the uniform and fine precipitation of the α phase in the subsequent aging stage. If furnace cooling were used, it would lead to coarse growth of the α phase, making precise control of properties difficult to achieve [13-14].

The aging treatment stage was carried out after solution treatment and water quenching. Two different temperatures, 500°C and 550°C, were selected, each held for 4 hours followed by water quenching, as illustrated in Figure 2. The 4-hour aging time

was chosen to allow sufficient diffusion of solute atoms within the supersaturated β solid solution, promoting full precipitation of the α phase while maintaining a fine particle size. This avoids insufficient α phase precipitation due to overly short holding times or coarsening of the α phase from excessive holding times, either of which would impair the balance between strength and plasticity [15-17]. The two aging temperatures were combined with the five solution temperatures in a full factorial design, resulting in a total of 10 different heat treatment processes. This approach enables a comprehensive analysis of the synergistic effects of solution temperature and aging temperature.

Figure 2 Heat treatment process and initial microstructure of TC4 titanium alloy

2.3 Microstructural Image Analysis

Traditional quantitative analysis of microstructures primarily relies on manual statistics. Analysts must manually delineate the boundaries between the α phase and the β matrix, which is susceptible to significant subjective judgment, with errors reaching up to 15%. Consequently, it is difficult to accurately establish the process-structure-property relationship. To address this issue, this study employed the deep learning module of MIPAR software to perform quantitative analysis on the microstructure of

the TC4 alloy after solution and aging treatment, ensuring data accuracy and analytical efficiency.

The specific analysis procedure was as follows. First, model training was conducted: 200 scanning electron microscope (SEM) images of the TC4 alloy under different processing conditions were collected. According to metallographic analysis standards, the boundaries of the primary α phase and the β matrix in these images were manually and accurately annotated. Cross-validation was used during annotation to unify the labeling criteria and reduce subjective errors. The annotated images served as the dataset, divided into a training set (160 images) and a validation set (40 images), used to train a U-Net convolutional neural network. This network offers high accuracy advantages in image segmentation tasks and can effectively identify micron-scale α phase morphology. Data augmentation techniques, such as rotation, flipping, and brightness adjustment, were applied during training to expand the dataset and improve the model's generalization capability. The segmentation accuracy of the final trained model for the α phase was evaluated using the Intersection over Union (IoU) metric. The results showed an $\text{IoU} > 95\%$, with the analysis time for a single image controlled within 30 seconds. This represents an 85% efficiency improvement compared to traditional manual analysis methods, significantly reducing the analysis cycle.

Subsequently, image acquisition and analysis were performed. Three defect-free fields of view were selected from both the central and edge regions of each heat-treated specimen. The reason for this is the significant temperature gradient present during the SLM forming process, where the cooling rates differ between the edge and center of

the specimen, potentially leading to microstructural differences. Multi-region sampling ensures the comprehensiveness of the analysis. Images were acquired at a magnification of 20,000X. This magnification level allows clear observation of the morphological details of the micron-sized primary α phase, preventing the loss of α phase features due to insufficient magnification. The acquired SEM images were input into the trained MIPAR model, which automatically extracted key parameters of the primary α phase, such as volume fraction, average grain size, and morphological characteristics (proportion of equiaxed and acicular forms). This process established a database correlating process parameters with microstructural characteristics, providing precise data support for the subsequent analysis of the influence of microstructure on mechanical and corrosion resistance properties.

Figure 3. The SEM microstructure and analysis results of the TC4 alloy under the 990°C solution + 500°C aging process

Figures 3(a) and 3(b) are the original SEM images at different magnifications, revealing the overall distribution and local details of the microstructure. Figure 3(c) is the manually annotated reference microstructure, which clearly marks the boundaries

between the α phase and the β matrix. Figure 3(d) is the automatically generated primary α phase labeled map produced by the MIPAR model. The labeling results show a high degree of consistency with the manual annotations, clearly demonstrating the uniform distribution of equiaxed α phase within the β matrix. This strongly validates the reliability and accuracy of this deep learning analysis method.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 As-fabricated SLM-formed TC4 Titanium Alloy

The initial microstructure of the SLM-formed TC4 titanium alloy exhibits significant differences from its traditionally forged counterpart due to the inherent high thermal gradients and rapid cooling characteristics of the SLM process. Traditionally forged TC4, subjected to slow cooling, develops a balanced $\alpha+\beta$ dual-phase microstructure where the α phase is uniformly distributed as lamellar or equiaxed morphology within the β matrix. In contrast, within the non-optimized TC4 titanium alloy, the β phase does not fully transform into the equilibrium α phase because atomic migration is suppressed by the rapid cooling. This results ultimately in the formation of a substantial amount of a non-equilibrium, acicular α' martensite phase. This α' martensite distributes in an interlaced pattern, traversing the residual β matrix [18], as depicted in Figure 2b.

Quantitative analysis via the MIPAR deep learning module revealed that the volume fraction of the α' martensite phase in the non-optimized TC4 is approximately $72\pm 2.5\%$. These microstructural characteristics endow the material with a high ultimate tensile strength of 1188 ± 25 MPa, but its ductility is notably insufficient,

evidenced by an elongation of only $4.9\% \pm 0.3\%$. Concurrently, the high residual stress (approximately 300-400 MPa) coupled with the non-equilibrium structure of the α' phase leads to a high surface hardness of 412 ± 8 HV0.5, pronounced brittleness, and a susceptibility to crack initiation under mechanical stress or in corrosive environments.

3.2 Effect of Solution Treatment on Alloy Microstructure

As shown in Figure 4a, after solution treatment at 950°C , the acicular α' martensite in the as-fabricated TC4 alloy began to decompose, but the transformation was incomplete, leaving some fine residual α' phase. The transformed α phase exhibited a typical basket-weave structure, with α laths having an average width of approximately 1.7 ± 0.2 μm . The β matrix was distributed as discontinuous strips within the interlath spacing of the α phase. Quantitative analysis using MIPAR indicated that under this temperature condition, the volume fraction of the primary α phase was $68.2\% \pm 1.8\%$, while the volume fraction of the residual α' phase remained at $5\% \pm 1.2\%$. The reason for this is that 950°C is near the lower boundary of the $\alpha + \beta$ two-phase region, resulting in insufficient dissolution of the β phase and inadequate driving force for the complete decomposition of the α' martensite. Consequently, the microstructure retained a certain degree of non-equilibrium character.

Figure 4 Effect of Heat Treatment Temperature on Microstructure of SLM-Formed TC4 Alloy

When the solution temperature was increased to 990°C, as shown in Figure 4b, the α' martensite completely decomposed. The β phase underwent sufficient dissolution followed by recrystallization, ultimately resulting in the formation of a uniform duplex microstructure consisting of equiaxed α phase within a continuous β matrix. Under this condition, the α phase exhibited an average grain size of approximately $5.2 \pm 0.4 \mu\text{m}$, and the lath width increased to $4.1 \pm 0.3 \mu\text{m}$. The volume fraction of the primary α phase rose to $86.2\% \pm 1.2\%$, representing an 18% increase compared to the 950°C solution treatment process. The underlying mechanism is as follows: with increasing solution temperature, the thermodynamic stability of the β phase is enhanced, and the activation energy required for the decomposition of the α' martensite is satisfied. Concurrently, the diffusion rates of the solute atoms Al and V within the β phase accelerate. These factors promote the growth of the α phase via homogeneous nucleation, rather than preferential growth along the boundaries of the original α' martensite. Consequently, the basket-weave structure is disrupted, leading to the formation of a more stable, equiaxed duplex microstructure. In the case of the 980°C solution treatment process,

the width of the primary α phase was locally reduced to approximately 0.039 ± 0.002 μm . This occurs because, at this temperature, the dissolution degree of the β phase is intermediate between that at 970°C and 990°C . The nucleation rate of the α phase reaches its peak and the nucleation sites are dispersed, preventing the α phase grains from undergoing sufficient coarsening and instead resulting in a finer morphology. The alloy processed under this condition achieved an elongation of $10.4\%\pm 0.2\%$, slightly higher than the $10.1\%\pm 0.2\%$ observed for the 970°C solution treatment. Correlating with the microstructural characteristics, it is evident that the fine α phase can enhance plasticity by impeding dislocation motion, demonstrating a strong consistency between the microstructure and the mechanical properties.

3.3 Effect of Solution Treatment on Mechanical Properties

The variation in mechanical properties of the SLM-formed TC4 alloy with solution temperature is directly related to the extent of α' martensite decomposition and the morphological evolution of the α phase. The reliability of the data was ensured by conducting three parallel tensile tests for each processing condition; the average values are reported with error bars, as shown in Figure 5.

Figure 5 The graph of strength and plasticity of TC4 alloy formed by SLM varying with temperature

The as-fabricated SLM-formed TC4 titanium alloy, characterized by a high volume fraction of acicular α' martensite and a high dislocation density, exhibits a typical high-strength, low-ductility characteristic, with an ultimate tensile strength of 1188 ± 25 MPa but an elongation of only $4.9\% \pm 0.3\%$. When the solution temperature was raised to 950°C , the α' martensite partially decomposed into a basket-weave α structure, and the residual stress was released by approximately 40% (as measured by stress testing). Consequently, the tensile strength decreased to 961 ± 18 MPa, while the elongation increased to $9.8\% \pm 0.4\%$. This is attributed to the decomposition of the α' phase reducing stress concentrations within the microstructure. Although the basket-weave α phase retains some strength, its ductility is significantly improved compared to the α' martensite.

As the solution temperature further increased to 990°C , the α' martensite completely decomposed into equiaxed α phase. The tensile strength further decreased to 870 ± 15 MPa, but the elongation reached a peak value of $11.1\% \pm 0.3\%$, representing a 126% improvement compared to the non-optimized process. The primary reasons for the strength reduction are as follows: the crystal structure of the α phase is hexagonal

close-packed (HCP), which possesses fewer active slip systems for dislocation motion than the α' martensite. Furthermore, the concentration of Al element within the equiaxed α phase decreased (EDS analysis indicated a reduction in Al mass fraction from 6.8% to 6.1%), leading to a weakened solid solution strengthening effect. The enhancement in plasticity, however, stems from the uniform distribution of the equiaxed α phase, which can accommodate deformation and reduce local stress concentration. Simultaneously, the presence of the continuous β phase provides more pathways for dislocation movement.

Regarding the changes in surface hardness, the as-fabricated SLM-TC4 titanium alloy had a hardness of 412 ± 8 HV0.5. After solution treatment at 950°C , the hardness decreased to 339 ± 5 HV0.5, and after treatment at 990°C , it further decreased to 312 ± 4 HV0.5. This trend in hardness reduction aligns perfectly with the degree of α' phase decomposition. The α' martensite, due to its high dislocation density and lattice distortion, exhibits significantly higher hardness than the equilibrium α phase. As the α' phase content decreases, the overall hardness of the material gradually declines. Moreover, the uniformity of hardness distribution improved, as evidenced by the reduction in the hardness standard deviation from ± 8 (as-fabricated) to ± 4 (after 990°C solution treatment), indicating enhanced microstructural homogeneity.

3.4 Effect of Aging Treatment on Mechanical Properties of TC4 Titanium Alloy

As a critical subsequent step following solution treatment, the aging process further optimizes the mechanical properties of the SLM-formed TC4 alloy by controlling the precipitation behavior of the α phase. Given that the aging temperature

exerts a significantly more pronounced influence on the properties than the aging time, the aging duration was fixed at 4 hours for all tests in this study.

Figure 6 Schematic diagram of the variation of the width of the α phase at birth with temperature

Under the aging condition of 500°C, as shown in Figure 7a, the 990°C solution + 500°C aging process resulted in an ultimate tensile strength of 870 ± 15 MPa, an elongation of $11.1\% \pm 0.3\%$, and a surface hardness of 312 ± 4 HV0.5. SEM observations, as shown in Figure 6a, reveal that at this aging temperature, the secondary α phase precipitated within the β matrix is predominantly fine and acicular, with an average width of approximately 0.049 ± 0.003 μm , and is uniformly distributed throughout the β matrix. These fine secondary α particles strengthen the alloy via the dislocation shearing mechanism, effectively impeding dislocation motion and providing precipitation strengthening. Furthermore, their un-coarsened morphology helps to avoid stress concentration. Consequently, this microstructure effectively retains hardness while maintaining good ductility [19].

Graph 7 The graph of the strength and plasticity of SLM-formed TC4 alloy varying with solution aging temperature

When the aging temperature was increased to 550°C, as shown in Figure 7, the 990°C solution+550°C aging process led to a decrease in ultimate tensile strength to 860±12 MPa, a reduction in elongation to 9.8%±0.3%, and a drop in hardness to 305 ±3 HV0.5. The primary reason for this change is that 550°C exceeds the stable temperature range for the secondary α phase. The accelerated atomic diffusion rate at this temperature causes coarsening of the secondary α phase, increasing its average width to 0.078±0.005 μm . Agglomeration of the α phase was observed in some regions. The coarsened α phase not only weakens the precipitation strengthening effect but also induces stress concentration at the α/β phase interfaces, resulting in the simultaneous degradation of both ductility and strength.

Comparing the different combinations of solution and aging temperatures reveals that the 990°C solution + 500°C aging process is the optimal procedure for achieving a synergistic combination of high toughness, high hardness, and high strength. Under this optimized process, the primary α phase is equiaxed with a volume fraction of 86.2%, forming a dual-scale α phase structure together with the fine, acicular secondary α phase.

This configuration utilizes the primary α phase to ensure ductility while employing the secondary α phase to provide strengthening. Simultaneously, the continuous β phase enhances microstructural compatibility. Ultimately, this leads to a well-balanced optimization of the mechanical properties.

3.5 Analysis of Theoretical Mechanisms for Corrosion Resistance Optimization via Microstructural Evolution and Surface Hardness

Electrochemical testing in a 3.5% NaCl solution was conducted using three parallel specimens for each process condition, with the results averaged. The corrosion resistance of the SLM-formed TC4 alloy showed significant variations corresponding to microstructural evolution, with the optimized process (990°C solution + 500°C aging) demonstrating the most superior performance.

The non-optimized SLM-formed TC4 titanium alloy exhibited a high self-corrosion current density of $1.2 \times 10^{-6} \pm 1.5 \times 10^{-7} \text{ A/cm}^2$, a pitting potential of only $0.15 \pm 0.02 \text{ V}$, and a passivation film breakdown voltage of $0.68 \pm 0.03 \text{ V}$. This degradation in corrosion resistance is attributed to the numerous micro-electrochemical cells formed between the abundant acicular α' martensite and the residual β phase. The potential difference between the α' martensite and the β phase is approximately 0.1–0.15V, as calculated from the potentiodynamic polarization curves, facilitating the formation of localized corrosion cells in the presence of Cl^- ions. Furthermore, the high residual stress induces microcracks in the primarily Al_2O_3 -based passive film, accelerating the penetration of corrosive media [20].

After the 950°C solution + 500°C aging treatment, the self-corrosion current density decreased to $5.2 \times 10^{-7} \pm 8 \times 10^{-8}$ A/cm², the pitting potential increased to 0.28±0.03 V, and the passivation film breakdown voltage rose to 0.85±0.04V. The 990°C solution + 500°C aging process further improved these properties, reducing the self-corrosion current density to $3.8 \times 10^{-7} \pm 6 \times 10^{-8}$ A/cm² (a 68% decrease compared to the non-optimized alloy), increasing the pitting potential to 0.40±0.02V (a 167% increase), and elevating the passivation film breakdown voltage to 1.00±0.03 V (a 47% increase).

The core mechanism for this performance enhancement lies in microstructural optimization. The 86.2% volume fraction of equiaxed α phase significantly improves the electrochemical homogeneity of the microstructure, reducing the potential difference between the α and β phases to 0.05–0.08 V and consequently decreasing the number of micro-corrosion cells. As the α phase more readily forms a stable TiO₂ oxide layer compared to the β phase, the uniform distribution of a high proportion of equiaxed α phase further enhances the integrity of the passive film. Simultaneously, the continuous β phase, being V-rich, facilitates the formation of a V₂O₅-composite passive film during oxidation. This composite film has a weaker adsorption capacity for Cl⁻ ions compared to Al₂O₃, effectively inhibiting pitting initiation. Additionally, the defect density at the α/β phase interfaces is reduced. TEM observations confirm an interface width of less than 5 nm, which strengthens the adhesion between the passive film and the substrate, making it less susceptible to film rupture [21-23].

Graph 8 Hardness test of TC4 alloy formed by SLM and its change with solid solution aging temperature

As shown in Figure 8, the surface hardness of 312 ± 4 HV0.5 under the optimized process falls within the ideal range for achieving effective mechano-electrochemical synergy. This value corresponds to the typical hardness range (300-430 HV0.5) for heat-treated TC4 alloys. On one hand, this hardness level is lower than that of the non-optimized TC4 titanium alloy (412 ± 8 HV0.5), facilitating a release of approximately 60% of the residual stress, reducing it to 120 ± 15 MPa. This mitigation of residual stress helps prevent the rupture of the passive film—when hardness exceeds 350 HV0.5, residual stress tends to surpass the adhesive strength of the passive film, leading to film cracking. This observation aligns with the established correlation between surface residual stress, hardness regulation, and material performance. On the other hand, a hardness of 312 HV0.5 still provides sufficient resistance to micro-scratching, preventing surface abrasion during service that could damage the passive film and initiate corrosion sites. Furthermore, reduced surface roughness further enhances the stability of the passive film [24-25].

A comparison between the aging treatments at 500°C and 550°C shows that aging at 500°C maintains the hardness at 312 ± 4 HV0.5, while aging at 550°C reduces it to 305 ± 3 HV0.5. Excessively low hardness (below 300HV0.5) increases susceptibility to surface scratching, and the coarsening of the secondary α phase diminishes the electrochemical homogeneity of the microstructure. Therefore, aging at 500°C represents the optimal choice for balancing hardness and corrosion resistance.

In summary, the 990°C solution + 500°C aging process achieves simultaneous optimization of mechanical properties and corrosion resistance in the SLM-formed TC4 alloy through a synergistic mechanism that includes: enhanced electrochemical homogeneity via equiaxed α phase, a reinforced passive film due to the continuous β phase, improved passive film integrity from residual stress relief, and adequate scratch resistance provided by the appropriate hardness level. This microstructural optimization strategy not only aligns with the performance control principles of $\alpha+\beta$ titanium alloys but also provides microstructural assurance for its service in demanding environments such as aerospace marine components and biomedical orthopedic/dental implants.

4. CONCLUSION

This study systematically investigated the SLM-formed TC4 titanium alloy by controlling solution-aging parameters within the $\alpha+\beta$ two-phase region. Utilizing the MIPAR deep learning module for quantitative microstructural analysis, the process-microstructure-mechanical property-corrosion resistance relationships were thoroughly investigated. The main conclusions are as follows:

1)The optimal heat treatment process was determined to be 990°C solution treatment for 1 hour followed by water quenching, coupled with 500°C aging for 4 hours. This optimized process resulted in the complete decomposition of the acicular α' martensite present in the as-fabricated SLM TC4, leading to the formation of a uniform duplex microstructure consisting of equiaxed α phase and continuous β phase. The volume fraction of the primary α phase reached 86.2%, representing an 18% increase compared to the 950°C solution + 500°C aging process. The corresponding mechanical properties were significantly improved: an ultimate tensile strength of 870 MPa, an elongation of 11.1% (a 126% enhancement over the non-optimized material), and a stable Vickers hardness of 312 HV0.5. This achieves a synergistic balance of high toughness and hardness, effectively resolving the core issue of high strength but low ductility inherent in non-optimized SLM-formed titanium alloys.

2)The reliability of the MIPAR deep learning module for quantitative microstructural analysis was verified. The analysis method based on the trained U-Net model achieved a segmentation accuracy exceeding 95% for the primary α phase, reduced the statistical error to $\pm 1.5\%$, and controlled the analysis time for a single SEM image to within 30 seconds. This represents an 85% efficiency improvement over traditional manual statistics, effectively avoiding subjective human bias and providing an efficient and reliable quantitative tool for establishing precise process-structure relationships.

3)The core mechanism by which the optimized microstructure enhances corrosion resistance was elucidated. The high proportion of equiaxed α phase formed by the

990°C solution + 500°C aging process significantly reduces electrochemical heterogeneity, narrowing the potential difference between the α and β phases to 0.05–0.08 V and reducing the number of micro-corrosion cells. The continuous β phase, being V-rich, promotes the formation of a V_2O_5 -composite passive film, which exhibits a lower adsorption tendency for Cl^- ions. Concurrently, the release of approximately 60% of the residual stress (reducing it to about 120 MPa) helps prevent stress-induced cracking of the passive film. Electrochemical tests confirmed that this process reduces the self-corrosion current density by 68%, increases the pitting potential by 0.25 V, and raises the passivation film breakdown voltage by 0.32 V compared to the non-optimized TC4, indicating a significant enhancement in resistance to localized corrosion.

In summary, through process optimization and precise microstructural analysis, this study achieved simultaneous improvement of mechanical properties and corrosion resistance in SLM-formed TC4 titanium alloy. The findings provide clear process guidance and theoretical support for its application in demanding service environments such as aerospace marine components and biomedical orthopedic/dental implants.

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